

Examining Some Misconceptions About Islamic Women's Rights From Pakistan's Perspective

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Abstract

Men and women were not made to be subordinate to one another by Allah (SWT). In every aspect of their lives, Islam has protected women's rights and gender equality. Islam guarantees that men and women have equal rights and that there is no gender discrimination. But often the promise of Islam does not transfer into concrete acts because of the prevalent sociocultural norms and practices in Pakistan. Islam is the religion that freed Muslim women by granting them the same rights as their male counterparts. There are several false beliefs about women's rights in Islam that are common in Pakistan. Muslim women occasionally believed themselves to be oppressed and backward by their faith. Some people make the serious error of assuming that Islam is the source of all Muslim behavior and customs.

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Introduction

There is without a doubt no difference between men and women in Islam in terms of their relationship to Allah, as both are guaranteed the same reward for good behavior and the same penalty for bad behavior. According to Allah, women have rights over males that are comparable to men's rights over women. (2: 228) When addressing the faithful, the holy Quran frequently refers to both believing men and women to emphasize the equality of both sexes with regard to their respective responsibilities, rights, qualities, and merits. Islam is a religion that first gave women a place of honor and dignity because there was severe prejudice against women prior to the arrival of Islam. Inhumanity, inequality, and discrimination against women were all outlawed by Islam, which also provided a comprehensive code of conduct for both sexes. Prior to the advent of Islam, the pagans of the Arab world would force women to perform naked dances near the Ka'ba at their yearly fairs, treat women like slaves or chattels, and exclusively use them for sexual purposes. These women had no rights, dignity, honor, or rank (Doi, 1992). Islam treats men and women as being of the equal essence produced from one soul, in contrast to other religions who saw women as being possessed of intrinsic sin and wickedness and males as being possessed of inherent virtue and nobility. O people, remember your obligation to your Lord, who made you from a single soul, from which came its mate, and from which came countless men and women. (4: 2) It is sufficient to evaluate the condition of women prior to the development of Islam in order to comprehend the rights, honor, dignity, and status of women in Islam. They were treated at the time like slaves and frequently held positions worse than those of animals. The Prophet (peace be upon him) called for an end to all forms of violence against, or cruelty to, women. He treated them with grandeur. He urged the Muslims to respect women and fear Allah. And: "Those of you who treat your spouses the best are the greatest of you." Additionally, "A Muslim must not despise his wife, and if he is unhappy with one negative characteristic in her, let him be content with one positive quality." Additionally, "A Muslim is more perfect in his faith the more polite and courteous he is to his wife" (Doi, 1992). The Prophet (peace be upon him) commanded Muslims with great vehemence to treat women with respect. In his Farewell Pilgrimage (Hajj al-Wada), he commanded the participants, and through them all subsequent Muslims, to be respectful and kind to women. Fear Allah with regard to women, he commanded. Without a doubt, you married them with the blessing of Allah and declared their bodies to be lawful in accordance with His command. Regarding their access to food and clothing within your means, you have power over them, and they have power over you. (Doi, 1992). In Islam, both men and women are granted spiritual equality (Orakzai, 2014). Whoever commits good deeds, male or female, and is a believer, shall enter Paradise and they shall not be mistreated in the slightest, declares Allah. (4:125) However, many Muslim communities today do not consider women to have the same privileges that Islam grants them. Muslim cultures and customs are practised in many civilizations, and women in these societies are subjected to political oppression, cultural difficulties, and patriarchal aspects of their societies (Sechzer, 2004). Islam is very important in Pakistan because Muslims make up the majority of the population. Despite the Prophet's (peace be upon him) focus on gender equality and women's rights, dignity, and status, some have used the Quran and its

traditions to oppress and demean women by misinterpreting some of the text's verses (Khanum, 2008). Due to inadequate religious education, misinterpretations of the Qur'an, and Prophet (peace be upon him) tradition, there are many misconceptions about women's rights in Pakistan. In Pakistan, men retain the authority to explain religious laws since women are less knowledgeable about religion than men are. Because of this, patriarchal relevance is reflected and occasionally politicized (Siddika, & Khatun, 2014).

Before Islam, women's rights and status were as follows:

Women were treated like slaves in pre-Islamic Arabian paganism, with no rights or respect. Women would not receive an inheritance share from either their parents or their spouse. But in Islam, women are guaranteed a share of the husband's and parents' property (Rahman, 2008). Regular marriage as we understand it today was completely absent. There were certain marriage arrangements that could be considered fornication, prostitution, adultery, or polyandry (Faiz-ud-din, 2008). There were no restrictions on the number of women men may marry, and they were even permitted to wed two real sisters simultaneously (Rashid, 2004). However, marriage is prohibited in Islam because of kinship (prohibition due to marriage relationship). The Holy Qur'an states in this regard: "Forbidden for you (to marry) are the mothers of your wives and your stepdaughters that are in your laps (in charge of you) through your wives to whom you have gone in; but if you have not gone in to them, then there is no sin upon you (to marry them); and the wives of your sons whom you have begot-ten." (4: 23). The authority to divorce that the husband enjoyed was so unbounded and unfettered that he could divorce his wife whenever he wanted to without having to provide a reason that would be legal, and he could also undo his divorce and divorce again as often as he liked. He might falsely accuse his wife of being untruthful, divorce her, and leave her with such a reputation that it would deter future suitors, all while absolving himself of any maintenance or legal obligations. While Islam approved of dower as a form of respect for the wife, neither of the wives was able to get one (Faiz-ud-din, 2003). False accusations of being unchastely were commonly used to deny the wife her dower rights. Any person might receive her at his discretion thanks to her protector. Islam, however, made extensive and comprehensive changes to marriage regulations in order to respect women. Women were viewed as possessions, and if a husband couldn't pay his obligation during his lifetime, his creditor would inherit his wife as payment after his death (Saifee, Baloach, Sultan, & Khalid, 2012). Fathers were afraid if their newborn daughter was a girl because they believed that it was a bad omen. When a girl kid was born, fathers not only became unhappy but also felt ashamed. Prior to the advent of Islam, female children were subjected to outrageous discrimination, and some of them were even buried alive. The Prophet of Allah (peace be upon him) not only denounced this culture but also gave instructions to put an end to it. He explained to them that protecting their female offspring will serve as a shield between them and the wrath of Hell (Doi, 1992). The old Hindu law treated women like slaves with no inheritance rights (Uddin, & Hossain, 2017). If a woman's husband passed away while she was still living, she would have to burn herself to death when the body was burned (Doi, 1992). A widow who had to endure terrible suffering on a daily basis had no right to remarry. There were several horrifying traditions that had to be followed in Chinese society while having a girl. A female kid was considered a deplorable degradation, while a male child was considered an enormous gift from God (Saifee, Baloach, Sultan, & Khalid, 2012). Violence against women was intolerable in ancient Rome. Women were treated like slaves and had no rights, honor, or respect (Kabir, 2009). Men had the power to sell her or exile her, and a husband could summarily execute his wife for behaviors including drinking, poisoning, and substituting a fictitious child (Doi, 1992).

Islam's view of women's rights, honor, and dignity:

Islam forbids the exploitation of women by men and defends the rights, honor, dignity, and status of women through promoting gender equality and equal rights for men and women in all spheres of life. A woman who has legal personhood, the ability to contract, and the ability to make bequests in her own name is fully autonomous in the state of Israel. She has the same rights as males to practice any profession or business and to dispose of her possessions as she pleases. She is entitled to an inheritance in several capacities, including those of mother, wife, sister, and daughter. She is allowed to choose her husband at her leisure and is also given dower and maintenance rights. Women are respected and honourable in Islam, and men are commanded to treat their spouses with compassion and complete respect (Mohammad, & Lehmann, 2011). In Islam, mothers are given far more respect than everyone else. Numerous verses of the holy Quran enjoin Muslims to treat their mothers with respect and to provide for them well, even if they converted to another religion and continue to be atheists. The Prophet (peace be upon him) is adamant that the mother's rights come first (Doi, 1992). Islam holds women in the highest regard, saying that "if she is a wife, she is life partner; if she is a mother, heaven is at the mother's feet; and if she is a daughter, it is a blessing from Almighty Allah" (Soomro, & Khuhro, 2018).

Inheritance:

The pre-Islamic succession practices were unfair, vengeful, and unreasonable, and they frequently went against the rule of law (Akter, Rahman, & Dolon, 2012). Women were viewed as property, and regardless of their status as a mother, wife, daughter, or sister, they were not eligible to inherit. Males may always receive preferences because there was no explicit system in place for cognates and agnates. According to established customs, the closest male agnates received the deceased's full fortune while females and cognates were not included (Rashid,

2004). Islam guaranteed women's inheritance rights several centuries before western nations (Sechzer, 2004). Six types of people are never denied inheritance in Islam (Faiz-ud-din, 2008). Three of these six categories of people are male (father, spouse, and son), whereas the remaining three are female (mother, wife and daughter). In accordance with Islamic law, there are four men (the father, the husband, the true grandfather, and the uterine brother) and eight women (the wife, mother, daughter, son's daughter, true grandmother, full sister, consanguine sister, and uterine sister) among the twelve sharers (referred to as Quranic sharers, whose share is defined in the Quran) (Haq, 2009). Islam therefore does not devalue women while elevating males. Three circumstances could occur if a woman had the right to inherit as a mother. She may be entitled to either 1/6 of the residual (if the deceased person had a wife or husband and father) or 1/3 of the residue (if the deceased person did not have a kid or son's child or more than one brother or sister) (4:11). In two scenarios, the wife may be entitled to either 1/8 (if the deceased person had no children or son's children) or 1/4 (if the deceased person had children or son's children, regardless of age). (4:12). If there are just one or two girls and no sons, each daughter will receive half of the son; if there are two or more daughters and no sons, each daughter will receive two-thirds of the remaining share. (4:11). In addition, parents might equally divide their possessions between a son and a daughter (Khanum, 2008).

Marriage:

Men and women were created by Allah to complement one another, to procreate, and to live peacefully and tranquilly according to His commands and those of His Messenger. According to Allah, one of His signs is that He chose partners for you from among yourselves so that you can live in peace with them and that He has implanted love and mercy in your hearts. These unquestionably contain indicators for those who reflect. (30:21). Marriage is seen as the start of a family and the foundation of social life. It is obligatory (Wajib) for a man who is financially capable of paying the dower (Mahr) and supporting a wife and children, as well as physically fit, and who fears that, if he does not marry, he may be enticed to commit adultery (Zina). It is also obligatory for a woman who has no other legal means of support and fears that her sexual urge may drive her to commit adultery (Doi, 1992). It defends society and safeguards people against vice and immorality (Akter, Rahman, & Dolon, 2012). Because it is Allah's will that husband and wife love one another, support one another in attempts to preserve the human race, and raise and nurture their offspring to become faithful servants of Allah, marriage is viewed in Islam as an act for His pleasure. Marriage not only satisfies the sexual need of men and women, as it is also biologically predisposed to have sex, but also protects future generations (Hidayatullah & Hidayatullah, 1990). Islam places equal value on both the bride and the groom in marriage because, in order for a marriage to be legal, either party must accept the other party's proposal (Rashid, 2004). A legally binding marriage establishes shared inheritance rights, and the woman is then entitled to maintenance and dower. However, getting married does not grant the husband authority over the wife's person beyond what is permitted by law or a right to her belongings and possessions (Hidayatullah & Hidayatullah, 1990). In an Islamic marriage, women have the freedom to select their life spouse. No one has the right to compel her to choose her spouse or marry anyone, including her parents, siblings, brothers, or any other paternal or maternal guardian. Without her agreement, any marriage to a major woman who has already been married is universally void, and any marriage to a major virgin girl is illegal (Faiz-ud-din, 2008).

Dower:

Dower, which in pre-Islamic times was paid to the wife's father or another guardian and was used to denote presents (sadaka), might therefore be viewed as the selling price today. Islam permitted the payment of dower (mahr) to the wife in the case of a civil union as a sign of respect and not as a purchase price. Dower can be a monetary payment or any other sort of property that the wife is legally allowed to receive as a sign of respect from the husband. It cannot be viewed as payment or an exchange made to the woman in exchange for signing a marriage contract. Islam has emphasized the payment of dower and made it the husband's responsibility to do so. Give women (wives) their dower without conditions, the holy Quran commands. Consume the dower with good cheer if they themselves (the women) waive some of it back to you. (4:4). Pay dower (mahr) to your wife even if it's an iron ring, the Prophet (peace be upon him) commanded (Faiz-ud-din, 2008).

Maintenance

The topic of maintenance (nafaqa) is crucial in Muslim personal law. Not only is it legal, but paying for maintenance is also a sign of love (iba- dat). According to Islamic law, one of the essential and inalienable terms of the marriage contract is that the husband must pay the wife maintenance as compensation for the matrimonial constraint. Proper maintenance is a husband's obligation, and it is a duty that must be carried out happily without any criticism, hurt, or patronization (Faiz-ud-din, 2008). "Let him give her wife maintenance according to his ability," is a sacred command. (65:7). Regardless of whether she is a Muslim, an Infidel, poor, wealthy, old, or young when she surrenders herself to her husband, it is her husband's responsibility to provide her with adequate food, clothing, and housing (Rashid, 2004).

Divorce:

The Prophet (peace be upon him) was very disturbed by these pernicious divorce traditions and believed that their practice undermined the fabric of society. It was quite difficult to entirely eradicate this horrible custom. The Prophet (peace be upon him) had to elevate the growth of a primitive and uneducated community's intellect. If all attempts to reconcile have failed, divorce is authorized in cases of exceptional urgency according to Islam. Islam understood that it is preferable for husband and wife to peacefully part when it is no longer possible to maintain a marriage rather than being miserably linked together, which turns the house into a place of torment. A new chapter in the history of Eastern law was written with the correction of the Prophet Mohammad. He granted the wife the right to seek a partition on the basis of reasonable grounds, but he reserved the unfettered power of divorce by the husband. As the Prophet (peace be upon him) stated: "Of all things that Islam has authorised, divorce is the most loathed by Allah," divorce is discouraged even if it is permitted under certain conditions in Islam. (AbdDa'ud).

Delegated divorce (*Talaque-e-tafweez*):

Even if the husband has the primary authority to divorce, the wife may exercise this right to end the marriage if the husband delegated that authority to her (Soomro & Khuhro, 2018). This transfer of authority may take place before or after marriage. The authority thus granted to the woman is irrevocable and may be used even after the husband files a lawsuit seeking the restoration of their conjugal rights.

Redemption (*Khul'a*):

It refers to a consensual decision made by a husband and wife to end their marriage instead of the wife paying her husband a recommendation from her property (Faiz-ud-din, 2008). If a husband and wife's relationship is not harmonious, the wife has the right to request a divorce (*khul'a*) by abandoning her claim to the dower (Rashid, 2004). The Prophet of Islam (Sm) said, "Let a marriage be broken if a woman is prejudiced by it."

Mutual release (*Mubar'at*):

When either party in a marriage feels aversion, they are free to release one another without making any demands of one another. This type of divorce is an irrevocable divorce in which both parties to the marriage have the right to offer and the other party has the right to accept the divorce (Hidayatullah & Hidayatullah, 1990).

Right to Knowledge Seeking:

In Islam, both men and women are required to pursue education. In this regard, an unmarried woman has complete freedom to learn and can do so without interference from anyone. A married woman has the same right to education as a single woman, but she must respect her husband's and children's rights.

Ability to Select a Residence:

A lady is free to select her own place of residence. A married woman must remain at her husband's home because, according to Islam, it is the husband's responsibility to cater for his wife's needs. A married woman can choose where to live by taking her husband's abilities and benefits into consideration, as long as the family's dignity is appropriately upheld. She cannot claim residency in such a location in accordance with Islamic law, which would cause her husband some difficulty.

Conclusion

However, due to a lack of sufficient religious understanding, women's ignorance of their rights as stated in Islam, established practices, and men's dominant attitude, several misconceptions about women's rights in Islam are still prevalent in Pakistan's male-dominated culture. Men occasionally engage in some terrible customs and say they are dictated by Islam, however Islam never condones these bad customs, whether they are done to deprive or disgrace or blaspheme women, or for financial or political gain. Due to a lack of basic Islamic education, women have occasionally accused Islam of treating them unfairly, demeaning them, or depriving them. Proper Islamic knowledge and understanding of women is crucial in order to grasp the rights of women in Islam, comprehend their genuine place within the religion, and dispel common misconceptions about those rights. It is also required in order to shift men's dominant mentalities.

References:

- Ahmed, G. (1997). *Women's Rights and Family Values : Islamic and Modern Perspective*. Dhaka: Era Enterprise.
- Akter, S., Rahman, A. N. M. A., & Dolon, M. J. H. (2012). *Muslim Law*. Dhaka: Hira Publication.
- Doi, A. R. (1992). *Women in Shari'ah (Islamic Law) (4th Ed.)*. Kuala Lumpur: A. S. Noordeen.
- Faiz-ud-din, M. (2003). *Muslim Marriage and Statutory Law (2nd Ed.)*. Rajshahi: Aligor Library.
- Faiz-ud-din, M. (2008). *A Text Book on Islamic Law*. Dhaka: Shams Publications.
- Marcotte, R. D. (2003). How Far Have Reforms Gone in Islam? *Women's Studies International Forum*, 26, 153-166. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-5395\(03\)00017-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-5395(03)00017-7)
- Mohammad, I. J., & Lehmann, C. (2011). Women's Rights in Islam Regarding Marriage and Divorce. *Journal of Law and Practice*, 4, 1-13.
- Orakzai, S. B. (2014). The Rights of Women in Islam: The Question of "Public" and "Private"

- Spheres for Women's Rights and Empowerment in Muslim Societies. *Journal of Human Rights in the Commonwealth*, 2, 42-51. <https://doi.org/10.14296/jhrc.v2i1.2100>
- Sechzer, J. A. (2004). "Islam and Women: Where Tradition Meets Modernity": History and Interpretations of Islamic Women's Status. *Sex Roles*, 51, 263-272. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:SERS.0000046610.16101.e0>
- Hidayatullah, M., & Hidayatullah, A. (1990). *Principles of Mahomedan Law* (19th Ed.). Bombay: N. M. Tripathi Private Ltd.
- Khanum, R. A. (2008). *Feminism Status of Women and Islam*. *Empowerment*, 15, 67-78.

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